

Occurrence and distribution of the invasive rice black bugs *Scotinophara* spp. (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) in the Philippines

A.T. Barrion, R.C. Joshi, and L.S. Sebastian, Department of Agriculture-Philippine Rice Research Institute, Maligaya, Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija 3119, Philippines E-mail: atbarrion@philrice.gov.ph, rcjoshi@philrice.gov.ph, lsebastain@philrice.gov.ph

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is the staple diet of almost two-thirds of the world's human population and food to 1,400 species of rice-feeding invertebrates (Walker 1962, Barrion and Litsinger 1987). Of the rice-feeding invertebrates, 25 species are putative major and minor pests of rice in tropical Asia. Among the putative pests, the highly cryptic and invasive rice black bugs (RBB) of the genus *Scotinophara* Stål, 1867 (Pentatomidae: Podopinae) are emerging insect pests in irrigated and rainfed wetland rice fields in the Philippines. Upland rice is also prone to RBB infestation as observed recently in Landang, Datu, and Montawal in Maguindanao Province in April 2006 (AT Barrion, pers. obs.). Damage caused by the sap-feeding RBB is similar to that caused by rice stem borers—i.e., deadheart and whitehead are observed in the vegetative and reproductive growth stage, respectively (Barrion and Litsinger 1987). As a cryptic organism, limited information was known about RBB in the past (Gabriel 1975); previous damage attributed to stem borer may have been due to RBB. These pentatomid bugs are also potential vectors of plant diseases as damaged plants become stunted and leaf-feeding sites turn yellowish to dark brown, resembling a blast lesion (Lim 1975).

Based on labeled specimens loaned from different museums locally and abroad, RBB have been in the Philippines since the early 1900s. *Scotinophara serrata* was the first RBB reported in Palawan Island, Philippines (Banks 1909), followed by the collection of *S. tarsalis* (Vollenhoven) in Los Baños, Laguna. About four decades ago, six additional unidentified specimens belonging to three species [= to *S. serrata*, *S. latiuscula* Breddin, and *Scotinophara cinerea* (Le Guillou)] were collected in the vicinity of Manila in 1948 by an agricultural entomologist of the Bureau of Plant Industry. By 1983, six species had already been recorded in the Philippines (Miyamoto et al 1983). All but *S. coarctata* (Fabricius) and *S. latiuscula* Breddin damaged rice plants in the Philippines (Barrion and Litsinger 1987).

Scotinophara coarctata, the most destructive and highly invasive species based on recorded outbreaks and migration patterns in Palawan Island, was reported to have invaded the islands of Mindanao, Negros, Panay, Bohol, Siquijor, Leyte, and Samar between 1992 and 2003 (PhilRice 2006). In November and December 2005, RBB were found in Sorsogon Province located at the southern tip of Luzon Island, particularly in the municipalities of Bulan, Matnog, and Gubat. Several outbreaks were reported

thereafter and, by August 2006, RBB were all over in the nearby provinces of Bicol Region, except in Camarines Norte. At almost the same time, in July 2006, the RBB scared agriculture officers of Nueva Ecija and Bulacan, two major rice-producing provinces in Central Luzon, Philippines, as RBB were seen here for the first time. Farmers again used insecticides to kill the pest. In all instances, the highly invasive and cryptic pest was referred to as *S. coarctata*.

Because of the confused state of taxonomy of the RBB cryptic species complex, we have doubted earlier reports that only *S. coarctata* is the invasive pest species. To shed light on the problem, we hypothesized that RBB *S. coarctata* migrated from Palawan Island and established founding populations in the islands of Mindanao, Negros, Panay, Bohol, Leyte, and Luzon. Migration was believed to have been facilitated by the attraction of RBB to the strong 1,000-watt light bulbs used by fishermen in their boats. Upon docking in the respective ports, primarily to sell a fish catch, RBB were left at the dock sites. These black bugs either died at the new sites for lack of food or survived by moving into irrigated and rainfed rice areas that were commonly located 300–500 m away from the sea shores.

Fig. 1. Dorsal (top row) and lateral (bottom row) views of aedeagus of RBB from Palawan, Iloilo, and Sorsogon (left to right).

To validate our hypothesis, we collected RBB from six big islands representing 20 provinces in 2006 and borrowed Philippine RBB specimens from local and international museums representing 13 additional provinces within the same year (Table 1). All collected and loaned materials were taxonomically treated and compared with *S. coarctata* from Palawan previously identified by Professor S. Miyamoto from Japan. In conjunction with the hypothesis that RBB migrated through fishing vessels, we interviewed 22 fishermen with more than 10 years of fishing experience and inspected their vessels for remnants of RBB. These fishermen were regularly plying the sea routes from Palawan to Zamboanga City (n=12), Palawan-Negros Island (n=6),

and Palawan-Panay Island (n=4). A 10-point structured questionnaire was developed to elicit from the fishermen what they knew about RBB movement through their boats (Table 2).

We also monitored farmers' irrigated rice fields between 55 and 95 days after transplanting. We also checked the stubbles left after harvest to determine the population density of RBB. The sample size used was 25 randomly selected hills per field in each of the irrigated rice fields and stubbles. The number of RBB (egg masses, number of eggs per egg mass, nymphs and nymphal stages, and adults) was counted and recorded. The data gathered will be used to advise farmers on how to manage RBB effectively.

Our findings showed that *S.*

coarctata (Fabricius) was present only in Palawan Island and has not yet been found in other islands, contrary to earlier reports of bug invasion in irrigated rice fields in Mindanao, Negros, Panay, Leyte, Bohol, and Luzon. Based on more than 2,500 specimens examined, the Philippines has 24 species of RBB belonging to four groups: *tarsalis* (one species), *serrata* (two species), *lurida* (five species), and *coarctata* (16 species). Different species were present in these six islands, most of which, however, belong to the *coarctata* group (Table 1). *S. serrata*, *S. latiuscula*, and all members of the *coarctata* group were collected from rice fields. The rest were collected from light traps.

Population density of RBB based on a sample size of 25 hills

Table 1. Incidence of rice black bugs in the Philippines with notes on their date of occurrence, distribution, and population density in the field.

Site (island/province)	Date of collection (Mo/year)	Source of specimens ^a	Fields examined (no.)	RBB 25 hills ⁻¹ (no.)		RBB hill ⁻¹ (no.) (R + S)	Scotinophara species identified
				Rice	Stubbles		
LUZON							
Albay	Feb 2006	FC	82	64	580	0.30	Species A
Camarines Sur	Apr 1965	LM					<i>S. tarsalis</i>
	Jul 1973	LM					Species B
	Nov 2006	FC	60	0	514	0.34	Species A
Sorsogon	Feb 2006	FC	102	186	1,014	0.50	Species A
Laguna	Apr b 1909,						
	Oct 1976	LM					<i>S. tarsalis</i>
	Oct 1948, Jul 1953-54,						
	Jun and Sep 1956,	LM					<i>S. latiuscula</i>
	Jun 1959, Nov 1981-82	LM					Species C
	Oct 1971, May 1972	LM					Species D
Manila	Aug 1948	LM					<i>S. cinerea</i>
							<i>S. latiuscula</i>
							<i>S. serrata</i>
Nueva Ecija	Jul 2006	LT	20	0	0	0	<i>S. latiuscula</i>
Nueva Vizcaya	Apr 1972	LM					Species B
Tarlac	Apr 1972	LM					Species B
Pangasinan	Jun 1953	LM					<i>S. latiuscula</i>
Ilocos Sur	May 1972	LM					Species D
Kalinga	Apr 1972	LM					Species D
Mt. Province	Jun 1951, May 1964	LM					Species E
PALAWAN							
Palawan	Aprb 1909	LM					<i>S. serrata</i>
	Feb 1982, Mar 1985	LM					<i>S. coarctata</i>
PANAY							
Capiz	Jun 1951	LM					<i>S. latiuscula</i>
Iloilo	May 2006	FC					Species F
Roxas	May 1951	LM					<i>S. latiuscula</i>
NEGROS							
Negros Occidental	Nov 1998,	LM,					
	Aug 2006	FC	16	0	0	0	Species G
LEYTE							
Leyte	Apr 1952	LM					<i>S. serrata</i>
MINDANAO							
Agusan del Sur	Nov 1959,	LM,					<i>S. tarsalis</i>
	Apr 2006	FC	50	26	348	0.38	Species H
Agusan del Norte	Sep 2006,	FC	1				<i>S. tarsalis</i>
	Apr 2006	FC,	28	0	24	0.03	Species H
Davao del Sur	Aprb 1909	LM					<i>S. tarsalis</i>
Lanao del Norte	Jan 2007	FC	6	568	34	5.05	Species M
Maguindanao	Apr 2006	FC	18	0	64	0.14	Species K and L
North Cotabato	Nov 1997						
	Apr 2006	LM					Species N
		FC	34	0	340	0.40	Species O
South Cotabato	Apr 2006	FC	28	5	176	0.26	Species P and Q
Sultan Kudarat	Apr 2006	FC	16	0	28	0.10	Species Q
Surigao	Aprb 1909		LM				
<i>S.tarsalis</i>							
Surigao del Norte	Apr 2006	FC	10	0	21	0.10	Species R
Surigao del Sur	Apr 2006	FC	10	12	86	0.40	Species R
Zamboanga del Norte	Nov 1959	LM					<i>S. tarsalis</i>
	Oct 1959	LM					Species S
	Nov-Dec 2006	LM					Species M
Zamboanga del Sur	Jan 2007	FC	15	106	944	2.8	Species M

^aFC = field collected; LM = loaned materials; LT = light trap. ^bNot sure of exact month.

Table 2. A 10-point structured questionnaire used in the fishermen's interview.^o

Question	Response (%)		
	Palawan-Negros (n=6)	Palawan-Panay (n=4)	Palawan-Zamboanga City (n=12)
1. Kind of job			
1.1 Fisherman	50	100	75
1.2 Farmer	50		16.7
1.3 Construction worker			8.3
2. Fishing experience			
2.1 10-15 years	16.7	25	16.7
2.2 16-20 years	16.7	25	16.7
2.3 > 21 years	66.6	50	66.6
3. Do they know the insects?	Yes [100]	Yes [100]	Yes [100]
3.1 Are insects good or bad?	Bad [100]	Yes [75]; bad [25]	Bad [100]
3.1.1 Nuisance	Yes [100]	Yes [100]	Yes [75]; Ni [25]
3.1.2 Bite	Yes [33]; Ni [67]	Yes [100]	Yes [100]
3.1.3 Damage crops	Ni	Ni [100]	Yes [25]; Ni [75]
3.2 Have seen mosquitoes?	Yes [100]	Yes [100]	Yes [100]
3.3 Have seen flies?	No [100]	Yes [100]	Yes [100]
3.4 Have seen ants?	Yes [100]	Yes [100]	Yes [100]
3.5 Have seen termites?	Yes [100]	Yes [75]; No [25]	Yes [100]
3.6 Have seen beetles?	No [100]	Yes [50]; Ni [50]	Yes [100]
3.7 Have seen RBB?	Yes [100]	Yes [25]; No [75]	Yes [8]; No [92]
4. Have seen RBB?	No [67]; Ni [33]	Ni [100]	No [100]
4.1. Smell	Pungent	Ni [100]	Ni [83]; Bad [17]
4.2. Size	Small	Small and slender [25]; Ni [75]	Small [8]; Ni [92]
4.3. Color	Blue [67]; black [33]	*	Blue [33.3]; Brown [16.7] Red [16.7] Ni [33.3]
5. Have experienced 3.1–3.6 swarms to light of fishing vessels?	All have experienced termite swarms.	All have experienced swarms of winged ants and green mosquitoes.	All have experienced swarms of brown-winged ants and mosquito.
6. Among 3.1–3.6, which of them swarm to lights?	Termites	Termites and green mosquitoes	Termites and mosquitoes
7. What do they do if there are insect swarms?	No action	No action	Put mask on their face
8. Upon docking, do fishermen clean the vessels?	All clean their vessels	All clean their vessels	All clean their vessels
9. Do they report incidence(s) of swarm to DA, BPI, QO for possible control?	All do not care	All do not care	All do not care
10. How far from the nearest land area do swarms get in?			
10.1 6–10 km			
10.2 > 11 km	Yes [100]	Yes [100] Yes [100]	Yes [50]; Ni [50] Yes [100]

^oNi = no idea; * = no response.

per field was very low. Across all fields, the range was 0–5.02 bugs per hill (Table 1). Moreover, there is no reason for alarm as majority of the RBB were in the old and newly harvested and abandoned stubbles. A do-nothing approach at this time is recommended, which is safer and more economical than the farmers' practice of spraying hazardous insecticides to control RBB. The best practice, however, is to cut the stubbles at ground level to remove the bugs' breeding habitats or to flood the field if water is available. This practice is necessary to remove the RBB's potential breeding grounds—the abandoned decaying stubbles capable of producing thousands of second-generation populations that swarm to light traps during full moon.

Fishermen interviews revealed that they have knowledge about some species of insects, particularly ants and mosquitoes, as they are always exposed to insect bites. The fishermen have commonly experienced swarms of winged termites (order Isoptera) and chironomids (order Diptera) attracted to lights on their boats, but not RBB, even at distances more than 10 km away from the shore. Similarly, fishermen mistakenly called chironomid flies green mosquitoes. Our findings from the interview showed that RBB may not have been transported by fishing vessels at all. Otherwise, a fisherman could have recognized the RBB that are attracted to street lights by the thousands in the villages. More so, the taxonomic investigation could have indicated

the presence of *S. coarctata* in the other islands.

The taxonomic investigation supported the results of fishermen interviews—that RBB have not been transported by fishing vessels at present. *S. coarctata* appears to be endemic in Palawan and other species exist in other islands. The discovery of 24 taxa of *Scotinophara* in the Philippines only reflects its diversity of occurrence and distribution in the different islands. To date, only two species of *Scotinophara* (*coarctata* and *latiuscula*) were found to be feeding on the rice plant.

Acknowledgment

We are deeply grateful to Mrs. Wilma Cuaterno, Mr. Prescillano Salazar, and Mr. George Karganilla, Bureau of Plant Industry, Department of Agriculture, San Andres, Manila, for providing

Fig. 2. General appearance of RBB species from Palawan (A), Iloilo (B), Sorsogon (C), and Laguna (D and E).

us access to their RBB museum collections. We thank the International Rice Research Institute, Philippines, and BIOTECH, University of the Philippines Los Baños, for allowing ATB the use of their equipment and other facilities.

References

Banks CS. 1909. *Rhynchota Palawanica*, Part 1: Heteroptera. Philipp. J. Sci. IVa:553-593.

Barrion AT, Litsinger JA. 1987. The bionomics, karyology, and chemical control of the node-

feeding black bug, *Scotinophara latiuscula* Breddin (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae), in the Philippines. J. Plant Prot. Trop. 4(1):37-54.

Gabriel B. 1975. Checklist of Philippine insects and mites of agricultural importance. Department of Entomology, UP Los Baños, Laguna. 75 p.

Lim GS. 1975. *Scotinophara coarctata* (F.) sheltered within rice hills. Rice Entomol. Newsl. 3:5.

Miyamoto S, Torres NA, Habibuddin BH, Montri R, Fujimura T, Thieng P, Mochida O. 1983. Emerging problems of pests

and diseases—the black bug in Southeast Asia. Paper presented at the International Rice Research Conference, 18-22 Apr 1983, International Rice Research Institute, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines. 33 p.

PhilRice (Philippine Rice Research Institute). 2006. Management of the rice black bug. Rice Tech. Bull. 31:1-14.

Walker HG. 1962. Preliminary list of insects and mites recorded on paddy rice. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization. 63 p. (mimeo.)

